

PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF SOCIO-CULTURAL MANAGEMENT

Socio-Cultural Management Journal

Volume 7 (2024), Number 1, pp. 84-103

doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2709-846X.1.2024.304780>

p-ISSN 2709-846X, e-ISSN 2709-9571

Original Research Article

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UDC: 005.3:004]:7:78

JEL Classification: L82, M39, O33, Z19

Received: 01/03/2024

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Digital Management in the Field of Art and Music Industry

Abstract: *Introduction.* In the modern information society, which is in a constant state of transformation and evolution, the role of technology and digitization in various fields of human activity is becoming increasingly significant. One area where the impact of digital innovation is particularly evident is the arts, namely the music industry. The development of digital technologies and online communications has brought significant changes to all music industry processes: from music content production to its promotion and distribution. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is to analyze the features of digital management in the field of art and music industry, identify unique challenges and opportunities for creators, musicians and other industry participants in the digital age by considering the key aspects of digital management. The work is based on dialectical, deductive, systemic and interdisciplinary approaches, which made it possible to generalize theoretical and practical achievements accumulated by society in the context of digital management. *Results.* The essence of digital management, its features in the field of art and music industry are revealed. The stages of digitalization as part of the process of adaptation and integration of new technologies in various spheres of activity are defined. The key components of digital management in the field of art and music industry have been identified. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty of the research results lies in deepening the understanding of the essence of digital management, its features in the field of art and the music industry. The significance of the study is found in the addition of cultural science with new theoretical provisions about digital management in the field of art, as well as in the possibility of using them in the process of increasing the efficiency of activities in the music industry in the digital era.

Keywords: digitalization, art, music industry, digital management.

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1. Introduction

The problem formulation. In a world where technological innovation is changing the way we interact and consume content, understanding digital technologies is critical to successful operation and development. Understanding digital management allows not only to adapt to rapidly changing market conditions, but also to forecast and shape it. Understanding technological trends and tools allows more efficient use of resources, optimization of processes and development of innovative development strategies.

In the context of art, understanding digital management becomes the key to unlocking new possibilities for creativity and interaction with the audience. However, the successful use of digital tools requires not only creative virtuosity but also an understanding of digital markets, data analytics, marketing strategies and promotion in the online space. Art in the digital world becomes not only a process of creativity, but also a business, where the successful implementation and distribution of works of art depends on the ability to effectively manage digital resources and interact with digital audiences.

In the music industry context, where digital platforms play an increasingly important role in the content distribution and monetization, understanding the principles of digital management becomes a key success factor. The ability to adapt to new music distribution formats, effectively use digital tools for marketing and promotion, and protect intellectual property in the digital environment are all becoming necessary for recognition and long-term success.

In-depth study and understanding of digital management is a key element of successful adaptation to modern realities, ensuring competitive advantage and sustainable development in the rapidly changing digital world.

State study of the problem. The study of the available literature shows that there are several aspects and facets of digitalization that are analyzed by various sciences, including sociology, computer science, cultural studies, psychology, philosophy, economics, management, and others.

The research of management and control in modern realities is devoted to the work of many scientists who investigate various aspects of organizational effectiveness, strategic management, leadership, innovation, as well as the application of modern technologies and methods: Ichak Adizes (2004), Peter Drucker (2007), Jeanne Ross, Cynthia Beath and Martin Mocker (2019), and others. Issues of management in the field of culture and art are highlighted in the works of Yaroslav Martynyshyn, Olena Khlystun, Yelena Kovalenko, and Larysa Butko (Martynyshyn et al., 2020, 2022, 2023; Martynyshyn & Khlystun, 2018; Martynyshyn & Kovalenko, 2018; Kovalenko, 2017, 2018, 2023; Butko et al., 2022, 2023; Vasylenko, 2022; Pushmin, 2023) and other Ukrainian and foreign scientists.

Authors such as Kevin Kelly (1995), Clayton Christensen (1997), Mark Baker (2014), Erik Brynjolfsson and Andrew McAfee (2014), Martin Ford (2015), Michael Moss, Barbara Endicott-Popovsky and Marc Dupuis (2015), Yaroslav Martynyshyn and Yelena Kovalenko (2016), Melissa Terras, Julianne Nyhan and Edward Vanhoutte (2016), Tom Goodwin (2018), Efraim Turban, Carol Pollard and Gregory Wood (2018), in their works, address the topic of digitization, digital transformation, and technologies that have a significant impact across all fields life activities Their research highlights the importance of adapting to the digital age, the impact of technological innovation on business processes, society and culture, as well as the opportunities and challenges facing today's society in the context of digital development.

The topics of digital management, digital marketing and other important aspects of digital management are discussed in the works of such authors as Charles A. O'Reilly and Michael Tushman (2004), Taylor Olson (2015), David Scott (2015), Dave Chaffey and Fiona Ellis-Chadwick (2019), and others. Their work has helped shape the understanding of basic principles and strategies in the field of digital governance, as well as identify the challenges and opportunities facing society in the digital age.

Authors such as Jason Potts, Stuart Cunningham, John Hartley and Paul Ormerod (2008) presented research on the interaction of digital technologies with cultural and artistic processes, the impact of digitalization on cultural heritage, the creation and distribution of digital content in the modern world, and other aspects of the fusion of digital and cultural spheres. Katherine Hayles (2012), Edward Shanken (2014), and others.

The study of the music industry and the impact of digitalization on it is the focus of many modern researchers and scientists: Jim Rogers (2013), Peter Tschmuck (2012), Patrik Wikström (2013), Andrew Dubber (2011), Tim Anderson (2014), Andrew Leyshon (2014), Steve Gordon (2015), Mark Katz (2010), Jeremy Morris (2015), Nick Prior (2018), Donald Passman (2019), David Kusek and Gerd Leonhard (2005), Daniel Nordgard (2018). Their work aims to understand the changes taking place in the music industry as a result of digital transformation, as well as to identify new opportunities and challenges facing musicians, producers, rights owners and consumers of music in today's digital world.

Unresolved issues. While emphasizing the importance of these scientists' research, it should be noted that there are still many unresolved issues in this area today. In particular, digital management in the field of art and music industry remains poorly studied. There is a lack of clear definition and understanding of nature, structure and functions of digital management in these sectors. Further research and study of control systems in the digital space is necessary. This includes studying best practices, various tools and technologies, as well as adapting existing management models to new digital realities.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose and research tasks. The purpose of the article is to substantiate the theoretical foundations of digital management, its features in the field of art, in particular in the music industry, which will deepen the understanding of the effective use of digital technologies and tools in the management of cultural projects.

Objectives of the study:

- consider the phenomenon of digitization as a significant challenge for modern society, identifying its key aspects;
- reveal the essence and basic principles of digital management;
- identify the features of digital management in the field of art and music industry.

Methodology and methods. The main works of modern domestic and foreign scientists in the fields of music industry, art, cultural studies, digitalization, management, digital and social management served as the theoretical basis of the research.

The methodological basis of the research is the dialectical principle of cognition, systemic, deductive and interdisciplinary approaches. Based on dialectical and systemic approaches, the author examines the interaction between digital management and the features of the art and music industry, revealing how digital technologies affect the processes of management, creation and distribution of artistic and musical works, as well as their audience perception.

Deductive and systemic approaches make it possible to consistently and logically analyze the features and importance of the application of digital management in this field, to identify patterns and generalize the obtained results to formulate general principles of digital management in the field of art and music industry.

The interdisciplinary approach contributes to the comprehensive study of the impact of digital management on art and music, allowing to look at this problem through the prism of different scientific disciplines, such as information technology, management, sociology and cultural studies. It helps to gain an understanding of the complex system of interactions between digital technologies and the art and music industries.

Information base. The information base of the research consists of scientific works of domestic and foreign scientists related to issues of digitization and management in the field of the art and music industry. These studies provide valuable information regarding the impact of digital technologies on various aspects of artistic and musical creativity, as well as the organization of management processes in this field. As an empirical basis for confirming the conceptual foundations of digital management, and the features of its application

in the field of art, including the music industry, the results of own research were used. These studies were conducted based on analytics and the generalization of practical experience in this field, including the analysis of existing strategies, trends in digital technologies development, and their impact on management processes and the creative sphere.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Digitization as a challenge for modern society

Modern science is increasingly paying attention to the phenomenon of digitization as a significant challenge for modern society. With the development of digital technologies and the availability of the Internet, significant changes are taking place in the field of art, resulting in new forms of creation, distribution and perception of creativity. In the context of the music industry, it is impossible not to recognize the importance of digitalization for the effective management of creative processes and the successful promotion of music projects. Thanks to the global Internet, music content today spreads rapidly around the world, providing instant interaction between musicians, their fans and different cultures of the world.

Digitalization refers to the global trend towards the general use of digital information in all areas of society, when it becomes the main driver of global social development, which improves the quality of life, from being a tool for improving individual, private aspects of life.

Digitization is the process of converting analog information or processes into a digital format, large-scale implementation of digital technologies in various spheres of society. This term has become especially relevant in the context of the rapid development of information technologies and the transition from traditional methods of work and data storage to digital ones (Goodwin, 2018).

Digitization enables more efficient encoding, storage and transmission of information using standardized and discrete values, which improves accuracy, storage and reproducibility of data. It is based on the principles of discretization, quantization and coding, which allow information to be presented in the form of numbers and processed using digital technologies. The term “digitization” reflects an important stage of technology development aimed at formalizing and standardizing information processing using numerical representations, which contributes to increasing the efficiency and quality of working with data in various fields (Terras et al., 2016).

In the cultural sphere, digitization means the transition from traditional forms of archiving and provision of information to digital formats such as electronic libraries, archives, streaming platforms and other digital resources.

Digitization in the field of art is the process of introducing digital technologies and innovative approaches to transform and improve creative processes, creation, dissemination and perception of art. It encompasses the entire spectrum of artistic expression, including music, visual arts, theater, literature, and other forms of creativity. Digitization opens up new horizons for artists, allowing them to reach a global audience, interact with fans and colleagues, and rethink traditional approaches to art production and consumption. This process is accompanied by a revolution in the field of digital tools, online platforms and virtual spaces, which together form a new era for cultural and creative expression (Moss et al., 2015).

Digitization in the music industry is the process of penetration and integration of digital technologies into all aspects of music production, from the creation of music content to its distribution and consumption (Tschmuck, 2012). It reimagines traditional methods of recording, processing and presenting music by transforming them into digital formats, enabling easy access to, storage and sharing of musical works over the Internet. Digitization opens up new avenues for musicians, producers and listeners, making it easier to collaborate, create and share music anywhere in the world. This process also brought new models of distribution and monetization of music content, changing the ways of interaction between artists and the public (Anderson, 2014).

Digital technologies cover the processes of collecting, storing, processing, searching, transmitting and displaying data in electronic form. Digital technology is a broad term that describes the use of digital information and computer systems to process, transmit, and store data. They are based on the presentation of information in the form of discrete (digital) values, unlike analog ones, which are continuous in nature. Digital technologies include computers, the Internet, mobile devices, software, digital networks, electronics and other technical means aimed at processing and transmitting data. They are widely used in various fields (Christensen, 1997).

In today's dynamic and digital society, there are constant challenges and opportunities provided by digital technologies. This evolutionary process, which emphasizes the importance of adapting to today's digital world, covers different areas of life and activity. The process of adaptation and integration of these technologies in different areas leads to consistent change and development, defining key stages in this context. This evolutionary process can be represented in the form of three key stages: digitization, digitalization and digital transformation (*Figure 1*).

Digitization is the initial step that involves converting physical data into a digital format, creating the basic infrastructure for further changes. This stage includes the description of an object, image, or audio-video signal (in analog

form) in the form of a set of discrete digital measurements of this signal, with the help of one or another equipment, that is, converting it into a digital form suitable for recording on electronic media (Wikström, 2013). Next comes digitalization, focused on optimizing processes through digital tools and technologies, followed by digital transformation, which represents a strategic stage. Successful completion of these stages not only increases the efficiency of various industries, but also makes organizations and industries more prepared for the challenges of the modern digital world, ensuring long-term sustainability and innovative development (Katz, 2010).

Figure 1. Digitization stages

Source: own development

A modern concept in the art and music industry related to digitization is digital transformation – the improvement of creative processes, strategies, operations, products, marketing approaches, goals and other aspects based on new digital technologies. Digital transformation in this context can be seen as rethinking approaches to project management, introducing new technologies into the creative process, and adapting to changes in the cultural environment. This concept corresponds to the ideas of the managerial revolution put forward by various authors, such as *Peter Drucker* (2007), *Ichak Adizes* (2004) and others. In this context, digital transformation becomes a key factor in the successful adaptation of art to modern challenges and opportunities.

Digital transformation is a strategic and organizational process aimed at integrating digital technologies into various aspects of an organization's or industry's activities to increase efficiency, optimize business processes, improve interaction with customers, and create new digital opportunities. It includes changes in strategy, culture, operating models and the use of technology to adapt to modern challenges and market demands. Digital transformation seeks not only to automate existing processes, but also to rethink them taking into account new digital tools and technologies (Baker, 2014).

Therefore, digitalization is an integral process of the modern era, which has a profound impact on all spheres of life. It brings both new opportunities and new challenges, demanding flexibility, adaptability and responsibility from society. Therefore, successfully dealing with this challenge requires a comprehensive approach that includes not only the development of technical skills, but also awareness of the ethical, social and legal aspects of digital transformation.

3.2. Digital management essence

In today's world, where digital technologies are becoming more and more integrated into various spheres of life, the concept of “digital management” is gaining special relevance. Digital management concept is closely related to the development of information technologies and their impact on the management of various areas – this gives an impetus to rethinking the theoretical and methodological foundations of management.

In the conditions of the modern information revolution, the proposals of *Peter Drucker* (2007) on the organization of information remain relevant not only in business, but also in the field of art. He emphasizes that effective information management is an integral part of successful functioning in the rapidly changing information space.

Information space is an environment in which information is exchanged, transmitted, stored and processed. It includes various communication channels, information carriers, databases, networks, data transmission systems and other means that ensure the availability and processing of information. Information space can encompass both physical environments, such as computer networks and data warehouses, and virtual spaces, including web platforms and electronic resources (Turban et al., 2018).

The issues of digital management research are widely described in foreign literature, and especially in popular science, which is actually a litmus test for the development of scientific progress. In particular, *Kevin Kelly* (1995) believes that “the information industry can significantly transform our lives, and shortly many old professions will disappear” (p. 177). Under these conditions, new professions will appear that will shape the direction of society. In turn, *Katherine Hayles* (2012) states that “the use of information technology has already caused drastic changes in the worldview, which will lead to people's awareness of themselves as individuals and as a species as a whole” (p. 62). *Martin Ford* (2015) states that “artificial intelligence can compete with human capabilities and intelligence, and, therefore, the author believes that machines will be able to replace many people and live their own social lives” (p. 166). *Charles O'Reilly* and *Michael Tushman* (2004) believe that “digitalization will enable companies to make real technological breakthroughs and produce new products” (p. 78). *Erik Brynjolfsson* and *Andrew McAfee* (2014) believe that “increasing the physical and intellectual capabilities of humanity requires the use of digital technologies that must transform our lives” (p. 95). Therefore, the implementation of digital management in the music industry becomes a key factor for the successful development of promotion strategies and effective interaction with the audience in the dynamic digital space.

The term “digital space” is formed from the word “digital”, which is related to the presentation of information in digital form, and “space”, which in this context means the environment or area where this information exists. This term is used to describe a wide range of electronic, computer and digital environments where information is created, transmitted, stored and processed. “Space” in this context refers to a virtual or electronic space created using digital technologies. This includes the Internet, databases, cloud computing, virtual worlds, and other electronic environments where information exists and interacts. Thus, the term “digital space” reflects the concept of a large field where digital technologies create electronic environments for the processing and exchange of information. It highlights the changes in the ways of interacting with information in the age of digital technologies and marks the virtual aspects of the information environment that expand and change the space of communication and knowledge exchange (Ross et al., 2019).

Digital technology has become an integral part of the art industry, facilitating rapid innovation in the music industry. In today's era of digital transformation, the music industry faces the challenges and opportunities presented by new technologies. One of the key elements of effective management in this context is digital management – a set of strategies and practices aimed at successfully managing music projects in the digital space. Understanding and mastering the essence of digital management in the music industry are becoming key success factors for artists, producers and others involved in the industry (Kusek & Leonhard, 2005).

The concept of “digital management” describes the management of processes and resources in the context of digital technologies, information management, processes and resources using digital, technological means and methods.

To date, the term “digital management” has not yet received a clear and universal definition, both in everyday communication and academic circles. This concept is a relatively new term that was formed in the context of the rapid development of digital technologies and their impact on management and control in various industries. In the commonly used sense, “digital management” is used to describe management strategies, approaches and methods based on the application of digital tools and technologies. However, due to the rapid pace of change in the field of digital innovation, this term can be perceived differently by different professionals and in different contexts.

The scientific community is also in the process of standardizing and clarifying specific definitions of these terms. Various researchers, scientists and practitioners contribute to the understanding of the essence of digital management, which creates a variety of interpretations and perspectives on these phenomena. The lack of an established and generally accepted definition of this term allows reflecting a wide range of its applications in modern management, leaving room for various interpretations and further research.

The term “digital management” is a combination of the words “digital” and “management”. This vocabulary reflects the essence and direction of this concept in light of modern technological transformations in the field of process management and organization. It describes the field of management where new technologies and digital tools are used to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of management processes, whether in business, culture or other fields (Kovalenko, 2018).

Digital management combines digital presentation idea and data processing with management methods and principles. It reflects the modern management paradigm in which digital technologies become an integral part of management strategies and methods, providing efficiency, flexibility and innovation in today's environment. This term arose as a result of a combination of technological changes associated with the transition to the digital form of storage, transmission, and processing of information in the field of management. It is a set of management methods, strategies and processes adapted to the digital environment (Martynshyn et al., 2020).

Therefore, digital management is a key aspect of modern management, focused on the effective use of digital technologies in various spheres of activity. This term combines approaches, methods and tools aimed at optimizing management processes, as well as at implementing information technology innovations. In the art and music industry, digital management is becoming an integral part of the development strategy, allowing to effectively manage creative projects, expand audiences and adapt the arts to the rapidly changing digital environment.

3.3. Features of digital management in the field of art and music industry

Digital management in the field of art is a set of strategies, methods and tools aimed at effective management and promotion of creative projects in the digital space. The essence of digital management in the arts is a combination of technological, marketing and organizational solutions, specially adapted to the unique challenges and opportunities inherent in the cultural sphere.

Digital management in art is based on the desire to integrate modern digital technologies with the creative process and management methods. This includes using social media, digital platforms, streaming services, websites, data analytics and other tools to maximize visibility and engagement with audiences. Digital management in art also implies active use of digital marketing, analysis of data on user behavior and creation of innovative projects capable of effectively competing in the digital space. It provides cultural participants with the means for creative expression and successful engagement with audiences in the digital age (Potts et al., 2008).

Digital marketing is a general term that describes strategies and methods of marketing goods and services using digital technologies to attract and retain potential customers. The main purpose of digital marketing is to promote the brand and increase sales through various marketing tactics. These methods include not only traditional means such as mobile technology, television and radio, but also a wide range of Internet tools, making the web space the main communication channel (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019).

Digital management in the field of creativity is a specialized field of management focused on the effective use of digital technologies and tools for the creative projects promotion and management. In the context of this industry, it covers aspects such as digital content creation and development, managing the online presence of creative personalities, analyzing data to optimize promotion strategies, and engaging with audiences through various digital channels. The main goal of digital management in the creative sphere is to ensure the sustainable and successful development of creative initiatives in the digital era. The process of effective management in the arts involves several key components, each of which plays an important role in achieving success (*Figure 2*).

Figure 2. Key components of digital management in the field of art

Source: own development

Nowadays, in the music industry, the introduction of digital technologies is becoming an integral part of the creative process of managing artistic projects. The development of digital platforms and tools allows not only music artists to effectively penetrate the market but also to quickly introduce innovations in musical content creation at all stages of production. The rapid development of information and communication technologies and economic processes emphasizes the relevance of research and implementation of digital management in the music industry (Shanken, 2014).

Digital management in the music industry is a set of strategies and methods aimed at the effective management and promotion of music projects in

the conditions of modern digital technologies. This term combines the concepts of effective management and innovative approaches in the digital environment aimed at maximizing the effectiveness of the promotion and monetization of musical creative works (Nordgard, 2018).

Digital management in the context of the music industry is a specific branch of management that deals with the effective use of digital technologies and tools to manage and promote music projects. Digital management in music projects covers the realization and promotion of music content, this comprehensive approach to music project management includes the development of strategy, planning, coordination and implementation of digital tools and technologies to achieve the goal (*Figure 3*).

Figure 3. The essence of digital management in the music industry

Source: own development

Digital management is a set of methods and strategies for managing information and content in a digital environment. In the context of the music industry, digital management refers to the management of digital assets. Digital assets are electronic, digital forms of assets that have value and can be used in a digital environment. In the context of the music industry, digital assets include digital files of music, albums, video content, as well as artists' activities and presence in the online space, such as social networks, streaming platforms, etc. (Gordon, 2015).

Digital management in music covers the entire life cycle of digital assets, from the creation and promotion of music content to its digital distribution and interaction with listeners. This process includes effectively managing streaming platforms, digital stores, and mastering social media to build and maintain

artists' online presence. Managing digital assets, including their effective use, promotion and monetization, is an important aspect of digital management in the music industry (Dubber, 2011).

Monetization is the process of converting any asset, resource or activity into funds or other forms of value. In the context of the music industry, monetization refers to ways to generate income from digital assets, sales of music, streaming platforms, music licensing, and other means. Successful monetization in music is an important aspect to support the sustainability and development of music projects and the industry in general (Prior, 2018).

Digital management in the music industry is a collection of innovative approaches and methods aimed at maximizing the visibility, accessibility and success of music projects in the online environment. The term covers a wide range of activities, from effective use of digital platforms and social media to data analysis and strategic planning. The essence of digital management in the music industry is the integration of modern information technologies and tools into the management practices of music projects (Passman, 2019).

The use of digital management in the music industry is due to the inherent impact of digital technologies on every stage of the life cycle of a music product – from creation and recording to distribution and monetization. The principles of digital management are based on close interaction with digital platforms, social networks, streaming services and other online resources, which creates new opportunities for promotion and interaction with the audience. The purpose of digital management in this context is not only to optimize the management of digital resources, but also to create strategies that contribute to attracting audiences, expanding the geography of influence, and strengthening the image of music projects in the digital era. Thus, effective mastery of digital management methods in the music industry becomes a key element of successful presence and development in the digital world (Leyshon, 2014).

Managing in the digital era requires specialized skills and expertise, and in this context, digital managers come to the fore. These professionals are key managers in the field of digital management, ensuring the effective implementation of digital strategies, technologies and processes in various sectors of activity. Their comprehensive approach to managing information, projects and business processes in the digital space makes them an integral part of modern business practices and creative industries (Martynyshyn et al., 2022).

The term “digital manager” does not have a widely accepted and established scientific definition. However, the following definition can be proposed, a digital manager is a management professional specializing in the application of digital technologies, tools and strategies in the context of managing information, projects or business processes. A digital manager strives to optimize

the use of digital resources, increase the efficiency of projects, and adapt business processes to the conditions of the digital environment. He is responsible for the development and implementation of the overall digital strategy, and may also manage the marketing, advertising and promotion of products or services in the digital environment. A digital manager has a wide range of responsibilities, which include: planning and monitoring the implementation of any projects related to the digital sphere (Olson, 2015).

In the context of the arts, a digital manager is a specialist who specializes in the effective management of creative processes and projects using digital technologies. It focuses on optimizing the use of digital resources, including online platforms, social networks, digital promotion tools and other technologies, to increase reach and influence in today's digital environment. A digital manager in the arts is also concerned with creating and maintaining the digital presence of artists, managing digital assets and interacting with audiences, seeking to combine creative potential with the capabilities of digital technologies to achieve optimal results in the arts and entertainment field (Scott, 2015).

A digital manager in the music industry is a specialist responsible for the effective use of digital technologies in the management of creative and music production processes. This professional is focused on using modern digital resources such as online platforms, social networks, streaming services and other digital tools to promote music projects and artists. A digital manager in the music industry is actively involved in shaping digital strategy, managing digital assets, including audio and video content, and creating and maintaining artists' digital presence online. It analyzes data and metrics using digital analytics tools to optimize promotion and audience engagement strategies in the dynamic digital environment of the music industry (Morris, 2015).

Summarizing, we can conclude that a digital manager in the field of art and music industry is a specialist who is engaged in the management and promotion of creative projects in the digital space. This professional has a deep understanding of digital technologies, online communication and media trends. He develops and implements digital strategies aimed at increasing the visibility and impact of creative projects on the Internet. It is focused on using various online platforms, social networks, streaming services and other digital channels to distribute and popularize content. The key tasks of a digital manager include building effective interaction with the audience, managing digital assets, monitoring analytics and constantly updating strategies in accordance with changes in the digital environment. This specialist becomes an indispensable link in the successful promotion and development of projects in the era of digital transformation (Rogers, 2013).

Therefore, digital management in the field of art, in particular in the music industry, is a necessary and important aspect of modern creative activity. Digital technologies open limitless possibilities for musicians. Achieving success in this industry requires an understanding of digital marketing tools and strategies, as well as the ability to stand out from the crowd. Effective use of digital management is becoming a key component of success for artists. Understanding the essence of digital management and applying modern strategies allow artists to reach a wider audience, recognition in the digital space and long-term success.

4. Conclusions

The article provides a systematic analysis of the digitization process, which is becoming a significant challenge for the modern world. Based on this analysis, the conceptual and terminological apparatus is revealed, definitions and descriptions of key concepts are presented, and the features and essence of digital management in the field of art, including the music industry, are highlighted. The results of the study allow us to draw the following conclusions:

1. Digitalization as a challenge to the modern world, which represents new technologies and a form of storage, presentation and distribution of information, changes and transformations in consciousness, is becoming an increasingly relevant object of study in science today. Digitalization refers to the global trend of using digital information in all spheres of society. Digitization is an integral process of the modern era, which deeply affects all spheres of social life. Digitization in the field of art is the process of introducing digital technologies and innovative approaches to transform and improve creative processes, creation, reproduction and perception of art. In the context of the music industry, digitization is the process of penetration and integration of digital technologies into all aspects of music production, from the creation of music content to its distribution and consumption. Digitization has a significant impact on the field of art and the music industry, opening up new opportunities for creativity and distribution of works, but successful adaptation to the digital environment requires constant updating of knowledge, analysis and understanding of new technologies, as well as the application of a comprehensive approach to their integration. The effective use of digital tools also requires flexibility and the ability to adapt to rapidly changing conditions, highlighting the need for constant development and adaptation in the context of digital transformation, which is a current concept in the arts and music industry.

2. In today's world, where digital technologies are becoming increasingly integrated into various spheres of life, the concept of "digital management" is gaining particular relevance. The concept of digital management is closely related to the development of information technologies and their impact on

the management of various areas. The concept of digital management was formed as a result of technological changes associated with the transition to a digital form of information storage, transmission and processing in the management of various spheres of activity. The term “digital management” is generally used to describe management strategies, approaches and methods based on the application of digital tools and technologies. It includes the idea of digital representation and data processing, as well as the development and implementation of innovative management methods aimed at increasing productivity and optimizing business processes. Digital management reflects a modern management paradigm in which digital technologies become an integral part of management strategies and methods. They provide efficiency and flexibility in modern conditions, stimulate the constant search for innovative solutions and approaches to management, contributing to the improvement of business processes and the achievement of strategic goals.

3. In the context of the arts, digital management becomes an integral part of the development strategy, allowing to effectively manage creative projects, expand the audience and adapt the arts to the rapidly changing digital environment. Digital management in the field of art is a set of strategies, methods and tools aimed at effective management and promotion of creative projects in the digital space. It is based on the desire to integrate modern digital technologies with the creative process and management methods. The essence of digital management in the arts is a combination of technological, marketing and organizational solutions, specially adapted to the unique challenges and opportunities inherent in the cultural sphere. In the music industry, digital management is a necessary and important aspect of modern creative activity. Digital management in the context of the music industry is a specific branch of management that deals with the effective use of digital technologies and tools to manage and promote projects. It combines the concepts of effective management and innovative approaches in the digital environment, aimed at maximizing the effectiveness of the promotion and monetization of musical works. Effective use of digital management, application of modern strategies allow artists to reach a wider audience, recognition in the digital space and long-term success.

The scientific novelty. The scientific novelty of the research results lies in deepening the understanding of the essence of digital management, determining its significance and features in the context of the sphere of art and the music industry.

The significance of the study. The significance of the research lies in the addition of cultural science with new theoretical provisions about digitization, digital management and their application in the field of art and the music industry.

Prospects for further research. Prospects for further research in this direction may include a deeper study of the influence of digital management on the processes of creativity and distribution of works of art and music. Additionally, such steps may include analyzing the effectiveness of various digital management strategies in the context of the development of cultural industries, as well as researching the impact of digitalization on the perception and consumption of cultural products.

Acknowledgement

This article is prepared according to the theme of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts within the framework of the topic: “Innovative Technologies, Entrepreneurship and Management in the Organization of Sustainable Development of the Fashion Industry and Show Business in Ukraine” (Project No. 0122U000727).

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the research supervisor Professor Yaroslav Martynyshyn for his valuable advice and support in carrying out this study.

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